

III ALAGOAS MULTIDISCIPLINARY CONGRESS ON CANCER

EMERGING TRENDS: THE INCREASE IN BREAST CANCER IN YOUNG WOMEN

Maria Vitória dos Santos (vitoriasantosbse@gmail.com) lead author, Ana Maria da Silva Claudino, João Carlos Souza dos Santos, Leandro Maia Leão, Roberto Lira Belo Neto, Larissa Lages Ferrer de Oliveira (Advisor)

Centro de Estudos Superior de Maceió (CESMAC), Maceió-AL

Introduction: Breast cancer is one of the most common cancers among women worldwide, with a significant increase in incidence over the last few decades. **Objective:** To challenge traditional perceptions about the age at risk for breast cancer and to raise important questions about emerging risk factors and prevention strategies. **Method and materials:** Literature review using academic databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar and Scopus. Search terms included "increase in breast cancer in young women", "breast cancer trends in young women" and "risk factors for breast cancer in young women". **Results:** Although generally associated with older women, recent epidemiological data reveal an alarming increase in breast cancer diagnoses in young women under the age of 40. Several factors have been proposed as contributors to the increase in breast cancer in young women, including lifestyle changes, diet, physical activity, exposure to chemicals, environmental and reproductive factors such as age at first menstruation. Young women present unique challenges, including late diagnosis due to lower clinical suspicion, tumor aggressiveness and impact on reproductive health. **Conclusion:** The increase in breast cancer in young women represents a worrying trend that requires a comprehensive response. Early identification of risk factors, public awareness, the development of prevention strategies and improved diagnosis and treatment are key to meeting this growing challenge.

Keywords: Women; Youth; Breast Cancer.

